

Mirza Athar Baig's novel "Hasan Ki Surte-e-Sahaya": Theme, Technique and Narration

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Abstract

Mirza Athar Baig's six-hundred-page novel "Hasan Ki Surat-e-Hal" is based on a four-page short story. He says that it is not possible to turn every story into a novel by giving it length. In 2009, when he wrote the short story "Uchatthy Khof Ki Daastan", he felt that there was scope for expansion in many parts of it... And when the process of committing this expansion to paper began, then the story kept coming out and finally this entire novel was ready. A funny situation of the facts that are happening in ordinary life is shown to us on a film level and what is happening in the film is reflected in real life. One of the special things about the present novel is that along with human characters, inanimate objects also move the story forward. For example, a table, a megaphone and a bottle of wine. According to the author, these objects are as important as human characters because in our daily lives, objects cannot be separated from humans. When we focus our attention on telling the history of objects, the world of human's freezes for a while and objects take center stage in our narrative. In this 'object-centered' situation, we experience the unique experience of seeing human stories from a different perspective.

Key Words: Mirza Athar Baig, "Hasan Ki Surat-e-Hal", "Uchatthy Khof Ki Daastan", 2009, film, table, megaphone, bottle of wine.

Literature Review

"Hasan Ki Surat-e-Hal" is a thick novel written by Mirza Athar Baig and is about six hundred pages long. The character "Hasan Raza Zaheer" created by the author fills the gaps in his life with his own thoughts, as every human being does, and at first glance, he takes practical steps to fill some of the gaps. Humans are very complex and the difference between their real life and their apparent life is related to their minds. Sometimes, some such events happen to a human being that a gap is created in his life. And then he adopts different tactics and makes various kinds of jokes to fill this gap. This is the conflict we see in the characters of this novel. There is such a difference between their real and apparent lives that this has created a gap in their lives.

"Hasan Ki Surat-e-Hal" explains various aspects of human psychology. The important necessities of life and basic human desires such as wealth, honor, fame and sex have been made a part of this novel. A special thing about this novel is that along with human characters,

it also includes inanimate objects. For example, a table, a megaphone and a bottle of wine. According to the author, these objects are as important as human characters. Because in our daily life, objects cannot be separated from humans. When we focus on telling the history of objects, the world of human's freezes for a while and objects take center stage in our narrative. This novel inhabits a strange and strange world. Civilizational microcosm, ideas of world domination through science, political ups and downs, the struggle to create world records, the style of film script writing and the repetition of eponymous characters make the novel interesting. In this novel, Mirza Athar Beg has used the technique of screenplay. The style, tone and technique of the novel are new experiences. Mirza Athar Baig's thoughts in this regard are as follows.

"Mein ne jo qarein paida kiye hain, mujhe un par mukammal bharosa hai. Jab mein koi nadir khayal paish karta hoon ya kisi aam khayal ko aik nadir andaaz mein paish karta hoon, toh mere qarein uss ko sarahatay hain. Aalami satah par jis tarah ka adab takhleeq ho raha hai, uss se sirf likhne wale hi aashna nahi, balkay qarein bhi jante hain ke aalami adab kis taraf jaa raha hai. Chunanche, mein apni tehreer mein koi anokha tajruba bhi karta hoon, toh mere qarein aik zer-e-lab muskurahat ke saath usse qubool kar lete hain."(1)

In "Hassan ki Soorat-e-Hal", Mirza Athar Baig has made the important necessities of human life and basic human desires, wealth, fame, honor and sex, the subject matter. The novel is set in a world of theater and film. In this world, there are enjoyable scenes on stage amidst the splendor of festivals and painful incidents behind the stage. This novel shows how a person struggles to fulfill his desires and what he does. This whole situation is presented to us by living, flesh-and-blood characters as well as some inanimate characters such as paperweight, mega weight, bottle, ring and round table, etc.

Iqbal Khurshid writes about "Hassan ki Soorat-e-Hal".

"Yeh novel Mirza Athar Baig ke deegar novelon se mukhtalif hai. Mumaasilat bas aik kulliya shikni ki khwahish jo aur shadeed ho gayi hai. Novel mein kayi kirdar aik jaise namon ke hamil hain. Yeh yaksaaniyat inteshar ko mehmeez karti hai. Aapko surrealism ki jhalakiyan milengi, kuch ajeeb-o-ghareeb idariati note. Sabse ahem bayaniye mein film making ki technique, jis ne novel ko nai jihat ata kar di hai. Darasal androon-e-novel aik film ban rahi hai. Jo 'yeh film nahi ban sakegi' aur 'yeh film zaroor bane gi' ke darmiyan jhoolti hai, lutf deti hai."(2)

This has been written in the editorial of the daily "Dunya" in this regard

"Zer-e-nazar novel, "Husn ki Soorat-e-Haal, Khaali... Jaghain... Pur Karo" ki kahani agar bayan karein, toh yeh Husn naam ke ek kirdar ke gird ghoomti hai. Husn ki aadat hai ke jab bhi safar ke dauran woh apni sawaari se bahar dekhta hai aur jab koi baat usse mutahaiyar ya hairaan karti hai ya tajassus ka baais banti hai, toh woh uss ke baare mein sochta hai ke yeh kya hai, kaise ho raha hai aur kyun ho raha hai... Aur is novel ke zimni title "Khaali... Jaghain... Pur Karo" mein Husn apne taur par unn waqiyat aur baton ki taujeehat talaash karta hai aur darasal yeh uss ki ek aadat hai. Iss kirdar ki zindagi mein is tarah ke jitne bhi

waqiyat paish aa rahe hain, mazkooor novel mein unn ko le kar musannif aage chalta hai aur is tarah yeh baat kahin ki kahin pahunch jaati hai."(3)

This quotation is also attached to this.

"Hassan ki Soorat-e-Hall" taqreeban 80 ki dahai se shuru hoti hai. Phir baad mein, aik film group Husn ke kirdar se mutasir ho kar is par film banana shuru karta hai. Yeh aik lambi dastaan hai ke kya yeh film group apne is mansoobe mein kamyab hota hai ya nahi? Is novel mein theatre ke ilawa, surrealism jaise deegar adabi masail par bhi taba azmai ki gayi hai. Is novel ki kahani koi seedhi seedhi kahani nahi, balkay is mein kaafi mukhtalif usloob istemal kiye gaye hain, lekin in tamam baton ke bawajood, ahem baat yeh hai ke is novel ko parhne mein koi mushkil paish nahi aati hai."(4)

The subtitle of this novel is "Khali Jagahen Pur Karo" and it is a character's commentary on real and apparent life.

"Yeh jaan'na namumkin hai ke kisi bhi shakhs ki zaati haqeeqi zindagi asal mein kya hoti hai."(5)

The novel's techniques include simple narrative style, editorial notes, book excerpts, and internal dialogues of the characters, thoughts, imagination, dreams, dialogues, Anila Saifi screenplay, scriptwriting and Saifi dragging. In addition to the simple narrative, there is an optional chapter, surprise editorial, internal dialogues of the characters, their dreams and imaginations also advance the story. The novel also has Anila. Saifi screenplay in which different scenes are presented according to the camera position, such as fade-in, top shot, long shot, pan shot, tracking shot, close shot, two shot, slow motion shot and zoom in. A map of the junk complex studio is also given. The author uses a different technique to bring the events to a rapid conclusion, which he talks about.

"Juzz ko kul par phailnay se rokne ke liye hum jazz ki aik izharati technique istemal karenge lekin tarameem aur izafon ke saath... magar is maqsad key liye woh maloma technique ziada istemal karenge jisay filmi grammar ke maahireen montage kehte hain aur jis ke zariye intehai mukhtasir waqt mein nazir ko taweel silsila waqeat ke zamani o makani pehluon aur kirdaron se mutaliq ahem maloomat faraham kar di jati hain aur is maqsad ke liye Dissolve, Fades, Double exposure aur baaz auqaat Split Screen ke tariqon se inhen baham marboot kar ke paish kiya jata hai. Iss tarah filmi kahani ki hafton kiya balkay barson par muheet paish raft chand minuteon mein samoi ja sakti hai."(6)

The style of the novel is modern. In one of his interviews, Mirza Athar Baig explained the style of Hassan's situation as follows.

*"Hum is novel ko aik tehzeebi *synthesis* keh sakte hain. Mein ne is novel mein is khittay ki tehzeeb ke tareekhi, saqafati, muasharti, jamaliyati, takhleeqi, wuqoofi aur bashriyati pehluon ko sametne aur un ko samajhne ki koshish ki hai. Is novel mein aik tarkeeb istemal ki gayi hai, *soorat-e-haal*, jise *state of affair* bhi keh sakte hain. Yeh aik aisi mukammal soorat-e-haal hai jis ka hamein aaj kal samna hai. Is novel ke markazi kirdar Hassan ki soch*

aur parkhne ke amal se is soorat-e-haal ka aaghaz hota hai, aur baad mein isi soorat-e-haal ke mutadid pehlu samne aate hain jis mein hum zindagi basar kar rahe hain.(7)

In "Hassan Ki Surat-e-Hal", there is a character named Hassan Raza Zaheer, whom the author describes in front of him. Since "Hassan Ki Surat-e-Hal" is a surrealist novel and in surrealism, the upheaval of time is a common thing and changing the order of time is the hallmark of surrealism. In this novel, Mirza Athar Baig has described the events in a complex way. Seeing different events in different ways at the same time and looking from the present to the past and future is found in this novel. How the psychology of the characters changes in a single moment and portraying their personalities physically and consciously is the achievement of Mirza Athar Baig's pen. Here we have a beautiful example of this in the case of Professor Safdar Sultan, who loses a valuable thesis on intellectual development. When the professor is studying abroad, his situation is different, when he is writing a thesis, the situation changes and when he loses the thesis, things change completely and he loses his senses. Sits. In this regard, Mirza Athar Baig says.

“Hum yeh dekhne nikalte hain ke Safdar Sultan aur Saeed Kamal naammi yeh dono kirdaar kin kin zamaanon mein... kaise kaise adwaar mein... kaise kaise roop mein aur kis kis mausam mein kabaariye Irshad ki dukaan par use yeh bataane ke liye pohncch sakte hain ke raddi mein bik jaane waali har cheez raddi nahi hoti.(8)

A special thing about "Hassan Ki Surat-e-Hal" is that along with human characters, inanimate objects also move the story forward. For example, a table, a megaphone, and a bottle of wine. The objects close to the author are also as important as the human characters because in our daily lives, objects cannot be separated from humans. When we focus our attention on telling the history of objects, the world of human's freezes for a while and objects take center stage. In this situation, we are faced with the unique experience of seeing human stories in a different perspective. The complete biographies and histories of the objects mentioned in "Hasan's Situation" are narrated. According to the author, objects have always been ignored and this tradition of being ignored is not acceptable in any way. The author makes a point in this regard.

*“Hum samajhte hain kafan dafan ka saaman bechne
Walon ki dukaan ke saamne rakhe takhte par gulaab
ke phoolon ki pattiyon aur gainde ke haaron ke darmiyaan ek kachhue ko baitha hua dekhna
husn*

*ki uchti manzar beeni ki tareekh ka sab se ghair ehtemaali waqiaa tha, magar zaahir
hai ke naa mumkin nahi tha. Is liye ye raye dena naa munaasib ho ga ke husn ne aise manazir
dekhne*

*shuru kar diye the jo haqeeqat mein koi wujood nahi rakhte the, balke husn toh khud ho sakta
hai ye meri nazar ka dhoka ho ko hamesha khauf ke aakhri naa qabil-e-tardeed mutabadil ke
taur par qubool kar liya karta tha. Lekin is ke saath hi kisi anokhi jibilli khud aagahi ki satah
par woh jaanta tha ki us ki haqeeqi zaati zindagi ghair ehtemaali aur naa mumkin ke*

darmiyaan pur khatar zaman o makaan mein hi parwaan charh sakti hai, aur sirf haqeeqi zaati zindagi hi nahi balke us ki zaahiri kamyabi aankhon mein aankhen daal kar na dekh sakne wale shakhs ki zindagi bhi ghair ehtemaali aur naa mumkin ki khutoot-e-wahdaani mein band thi.(9)

Through these inanimate objects, the author criticizes human greed, lust, murder, luxury, corruption, and sexual immorality. Although these inanimate objects do not have language, they do have history. The author has described that history. For example, there is a mention of a wine bottle in this novel. The empty bottle of wine that Irshad Kabariya cleans has a picture of a horseman from a famous Portuguese wine-making family on it. In the thirteenth century, a young man from this family, Alfonso Diaz Pizarro, entered the Moorish territory to participate in the Crusades and saw a Moor being flogged for drinking wine. He returned in fear and decided to spend the rest of his life making wine. Then he and his descendants became famous for making wine. This bottle reached Egypt after completing the aging period in the cellar of a winery in Lisbon for twenty years, from where an Egyptian friend gave it as a gift to his Pakistani friend, who after being an ambassador to many countries was now an important official in the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. When the owner's employees found it empty, they sold it to a junkyard. This story criticizes fear, greed, corruption, deceit and theft. The current novel also mentions the history of the megaphone and its conditions. In Chowk Khudadad, Jabbar is collecting sweets distributed in the joy of salvation from the Great Savior through a megaphone, when suddenly his megaphone breaks down. To find out the fault of the megaphone, it is necessary to go back to its past. This Japanese megaphone arrived here through an American firm called Wilson & Kidd and was lying with the police equipment. In a riot, the head of the guard wanted to warn the rioters through a megaphone, but the megaphone was broken due to the stones thrown by the rioters. Later, it reached the Lucky Star Theater through auction, which was activated by Master Yasin and made it usable. On the last night of the festival, the megaphone broke down again and was given to Jabbar, who was collecting tickets. The history of the megaphone includes mention of politics, democracy, corruption, and fine arts.

This novel also includes the story of a shameless paperweight that fell on Havaldar Safdar Sultan during a stone-pelting riot. Safdar Sultan put it in his pocket. But when he went home and saw this piece of marble, he was shocked because it was a shameless paperweight on which were statues of naked men and women hugging each other. In fact, this paperweight fell into the hands of rioters in the office of a multinational firm, while the zonal manager of this firm, Saeed Kamal, had given this paperweight as a gift from his fiancée Anila Bilal, who was working towards an advanced degree in stone carving and ceramics at the Art Academy of Milan in Italy. The story of the paperweight criticizes the illicit sexual desires of man. The story of the ring that was cut off from the finger of the injured hand of the head of the security force during the stone-pelting in the riot is also noteworthy. After treatment, the nurse returned the cut ring with strange expressions, which was a sign of his relationship with Anila

Bilal and had been given to him by his in-laws. When Saeed Kamal went to the goldsmith to repair the ring, he told him that it was not pure gold but gold plated on brass. Then Saeed Kamal understood the nurse's comments.

The story of the round table is chapter 20 in the novel. Thus, the round table is important among them all. The round table was cut from a mahogany tree that grew in the Amazon jungle 150 years ago and was made to order in Singapore, but the price did not reach its original owner and was the decoration of a casino. Here, the winner was killed by the loser while playing poker. When the casino closed, the table was taken to the ship's crew room by Captain Vincent, a friend of the casino owner. The SS Borneo Namiya ship fell victim to pirates during a sea voyage. The pirates shot and killed seven crew members sitting around the table in the crew room. The ship reached the shipwreck yard. Rehman Dada had the round table cleaned and taken to his friend's underground clinic where political opponents were tortured to death. When the clinic closed, the round table first went through Goga Furnitures and then Gogi Furnitures to Saeed Kamal's house. Here Anila had it placed in front of her Furnace to bake clay. In this house, the driver's granddaughter Khalida was murdered after being sexually assaulted and her body was cut into pieces and burned in the Furnace. Later, the table was moved to Durrani Building where it became the target of fights between the film group in the office of Sawang Productions and finally, in a broken state, it became a slaughterhouse for chickens at the butcher's house, true to its nature. The author, with the great power of his imagination, has presented the bloody story of the Round Table in a very terrifying way. In this story of the Round Table, the author's knowledge about various professions reflects the author's taste. Making tables from wood, playing poker, the casino business, the crew and travel of a seafaring ship, the activities of underground criminals, furniture making and its business, sculpture, film making, and finally the butchery business seem to be the basis of the author's knowledge.

“Magar hum apni is rai ki durusti pe hargiz israr nahi karein ge, kyuke jaisa ke pehle bhi arz kiya gaya, yeh jaan'na namumkin hai ke kisi bhi shakhs ki zaati haqeeqi zindagi asal mein kya hoti hai” (10)

The novel uses psychoanalysis. Psychoanalysis means to explore one's own states and find the empty spaces that remain in the human mind. In psychoanalysis, the subject is made to lie comfortably on the bed. He is instructed to immerse himself in himself and study it and express the thoughts that come to mind frankly and without hesitation. In this method, the memories and recollections buried in the subconscious are brought to the level of consciousness. No one else can guess what secrets we are hiding in our chests, let alone ourselves. It is only through psychoanalysis that we can know how many devils are hidden in an angel and how many angels are hidden in a devil. Constructive and positive ideas transform the human personality into a tower of strength, love, light and greatness. Every thought affects our body in a good or bad way. Mirza Athar Beg has completed the personality of Hassan Raza Zaheer through his psychological analysis of different characters in his "Situation".

Travel is important in Hassan Raza Zaheer's life and he sees different scenes through this journey. Many scenes leave blank spaces in his mind, so he fills these blank spaces through his psychological analysis, whether he adopts a practical method or uses his mind. We will discuss this further later. The second main character is Saifi who uses the blue register through dragging and in this way he tries to complete his personality by writing. Seth Safdar Sultan takes the help of Babli for this purpose and Babli uses Seth Safdar Sultan to make his film. Professor Safdar Sultan works on the theory of cultural rationalization and in this way he practically does the work of personal psychological analysis. Different characters named Saeed Kamal also do this work in their own way. Similarly, Irshad Kabadiya and Jabbar the collector also try to complete their incomplete personality through the junk complex. Sometimes the spirit of Shakespeare enters Irshad Kabadiya, although this is a funny situation, but this method has also been used by the author.

"Khali Jagahen Pul Karo" is the subtitle of the novel. The human mind is very complex. What is the real life of a person and what is the apparent life of a person? It is related to the human mind. There are many moments in a person's life that leave a void in his life. Sometimes this void is filled and sometimes these voids are not filled. A curiosity remains in the human mind. Mirza Athar Baig has taken up this aspect of the human mind in his novel Hassan. The character Hassan created by the author fills the voids in his life with some of his own thoughts, as every human does, and at first glance, he takes practical steps to fill some of the voids. Here are a few examples.

"To issi tarah Hassan Raza Zaheer ke saath chalte chalte hum dekhte hain ke uss ne na sirf toote hue aainay aur khoon ki lakeeron, dhaancha gaari mein kitaab, balkay barson par muheet aisay hi atkay khauf ke un ginat doosre lamhaat ke khaali pan ko bhi kayi mutabadil manzar naamon se pur kiya. Misalein itni ziyada hain ke sab bayan nahi ho saktin. Sarak ke kinare khari burqa posh khatoon aik lamhe ke liye naqaab uthati hai. Andar aik chehra nazar aata hai jo na aurat ka hai na mard ka, balkay shayad insaan ka hi nahi. Kis aur makhloq ka hai. Woh makhloq kaun hai? Aik dehati bus stop par har roz aik larka aur larki aik doosre ko mohabbat ke isharay karte nazar aate hain. Aik roz nazar nahi aate. Shaam wapsi par gaon ki atraaf mein do mukhtalif jaghon par do janazay nazar aate hain. Larka aur larki phir kabhi nazar nahi aate. Janazay kin ke thay? Waghaira waghaira. Hassan Raza Zaheer ne company ki gaari mein barson safar ke dauran aisay un ginat sawalon ke aisay imkani jawab talaash kiye jinhon ne usse har lihaaz se mutmain kar diya aur usse kabhi bhi kisi khauf lamhe ka peecha karne aur duniya mein barah-e-raast mudakhilat jaisi sangeen khilaaf warzi karne ki zaroorat pesh na aayi.(11)

This is a complex question: what is the real personal life of a person and what is the philosophy of the real personal life? Does a person live an apparent life or the life that he lives in his consciousness and subconscious? Is the apparent life a deception or is the conscious life a deception? The author has described the way in which a person sees these things as follows.

"Hum samjhte hain ke kafan dafan ka samaan bechne walon ki dukaan ke saamne rakhe takhte par gulab ke phoolon ki pattiyon aur gainde ke haaron ke darmiyaan aik kachway ko baitha hua dekhna husn ki uchatti manzar beeni ki tareekh ka sab se ghair ehtemali waqiya tha, lekin zaahir hai ke naa mumkin nahi tha is liye yeh raaye dena naa munaasib ho ga ke husn ne aise manazir dekhne shuru kar diye the jo haqeeqat mein koi wujood nahi rakhte the, balkay husn to khud ho sakta hai, 'yeh meri nazar ka dhoka ho' ko hamesha khauf ke aakhri naa qabil-e-tardeed mutabadil ke taur par qubool kar liya karta tha. Lekin is ke saath hi kisi anokhi jibilli khud aagahi ki satah par woh jaanta tha ke us ki haqeeqi zaati zindagi ghair ehtemali aur naa mumkin ke darmiyaan pur khatar zaman o makaan mein hi parwaan charh sakti hai aur sirf haqeeqi zaati zindagi hi nahi balkay us ki zahiri kamyabi aankhon mein aankhen daal kar na dekh sakne wale shakhs ki zindagi bhi ghair ehtemali aur naa mumkin ki khutoot-e-wahdani mein band thi.(12)

Sex is an important part of human life. It is included in the main goals of many people, like Safdar Sultan in this novel. Hassan's situation, although it is a complex novel, is still not devoid of mention of sex. Compared to "Ghulam Bagh" there is less mention of sex in this novel. Anila Bilal, who is the scriptwriter in the film, is used by Saeed Kamal to seduce Safdar Sultan sexually. Later, through Master Yasin Bali, Safdar Sultan is calmed down by Bubble, whose method is really new and interesting and strange for the general reader. This novel also includes mention of homosexuality. The concept of sexual discomfort is more common in this novel. Especially in Seth Safdar Sultan and Saeed Kamal. Saeed Kamal is famous as a lady killer, but in practical matters he is unemployed. Similarly, Saeed Kamal, a bodybuilder, suffers from sexual discomfort due to being poor. See a scene.

" "Slow motion shot: Biceps se barish ke qatron ko chatna-- Saeed Kamal ke chehre par aankhon mein lazzat ki aisi kaihiyat jo jinsi lazzat se mushabihat rakhti hai.(13)

One aspect of "Hassan Ki Surat-e-Hal" is the struggle of one generation of humans to dominate another. When Professor Safdar Sultan tries to fight for this, he has to face numerous problems. He wants to dominate through cultural rationalization. Similarly, Saifi is also a character who holds some strange and strange ideas. He is also strongly against the colonial system. While giving Jan a tour of the junk complex, at one point he says.

"Saifi: Haan, is ka surkh rang... jo tum dekh rahe ho, khoon hai. Isey humarey haan sadiyon se zulm ki har shakal, khandani, tehzeebi, mazhabi aur samraaji key khilaaf jid-o-jehad mein jaan deney walon key khoon se banaya gaya hai. Yaani, jaan deney ki woh soortein jin mein khoon kharij hota hai. Masalan... Jaan ka munh bigar jata hai... jaise ubkai aa rahi ho.(14)

According to the author, the West has achieved political dominance through democracy and they no longer need military coups here because they have made democracy a necessity for the people. The author has presented this drama of democracy in the form of a screenplay in the form of the political situation in the country in Chapter 4, Liberation from the Great Savior. Come and distribute sweets. The main square of the city is full of people celebrating the liberation from the Great Savior and distributing sweets. They are once again thanking

Allah for being liberated from the Great Savior and are stuffing colorful sweets into the mouths of the people walking by. Liberation from the Great Savior came after a long struggle. This struggle included provocative demonstrations, protests, riots, and riots. See a scene "Nijaat chahne walon ke hawale se buri buri khabrein aa rahi theen aur un ke saath bura karne ka order toh guzishsta shaam hi aa chuka tha... Muhafiz daste ke sarbarah ne megaphone ka rukh fasadiyon ki taraf kiya... Khabardar!"(15)

The rioters had already started attacking and were throwing stones, which left the head of the security force bleeding. Seeing the overwhelming power of the rioters, tear gas shells were fired and then firing started. The bullet of the miscreants killed the deputy inspector. The rioters looted shops and offices to make their demand for salvation stronger. Later, they set fire to the offices of multinational companies. These demonstrations continued for several days and finally, the great savior was saved. What a wonderful busy life the people have now. In Chapter 3 of the novel, the author refers to an English novel, The Clash, explaining the desire for dominance and the reason for the conflict.

"Novel ka markazi khayal yeh hai ke har saqafat, aur phir majmoi taur par har tehzeeb mein, apne ilawa baqi har saqafat aur tehzeeb par ghalba hasil karne, balkay ba'z ke haan toh dusron ko siray se teh-e-tegh kar dene ki jo shadeed khwahish payi jati hai, uski haqeeqi wajah saqafaati, ya tehzeebi, ya tarikhhi nahi balkay jiniyati hai(16)

Like "Ghulam Bagh", "Hasan Ki Soort-e-Hal" also shows the desire for dominance and the conflict between superiority and inferiority. The author has criticized Western civilization and its dominance through Saifi and the professor. In Ghulam Bagh, the emphasis is on writing a novel and in Hassan Ki Soort-e-Hal, on making a film. Neither the novel is written nor is the film made. The novelist and the entire film-making crew die accidentally. It is shown that all this is due to the desire for dominance and conflict. Amber Jaan kills Kabir because he takes possession of Zahra and the entire film-making crew is killed in a bomb blast while making a film as a result of sabotage by Western agencies.

Mirza Athar Baig himself has written a surrealist novel while explaining the making of a surrealist film in "Hasan Ki Surat-e-Hal". The novel contains supernatural events along with reality. For example, the arrival of Shakespeare's spirit in Irshad Kabadiye, Hope eating a cannibal plant, Professor Safdar Sultan generating electricity from jinn and preparing an extract of cannibal plants, and Hassan's seeing amazing scenes and filling in the blanks by adding imagination to reality are all part of surrealism. From the beginning to the end, the novel presents such events that meet the definition of surrealism. Asma Asghar writes about surrealism.

"Dar haqeeqat, Surrealism zahiri haqeeqat aur shoor ke مدار se bahar nikalne ki koshish karta hai -- yaani, maawara-e-haqeeqat, aik aur tarah ki haqeeqat ko paish karne ki justoojoo. Isi liye Surrealist fankaar la-shaoori aur ghair-mantiqi tareeqay kar par karband hota hai.(17)

The "Hassan Ki Surat-e-Hal" is a novel that is unique in terms of characters. In this novel, different characters with the same name are shown in different classes of human society and their situations are described. In Hassan's case, although the main characters are Saifi, Anila, Safdar Sultan, Saeed Kamal, Jabbar and Hassan Raza Zaheer and the minor characters are numerous, the repetition of the same-named characters is interesting, including the characters of Safdar Sultan, Saeed Kamal, Irshad, Jabbar, Anila and Sain. On page 43, Safdar Sultan is a professor, on page 78, a Havaladar, on page 100, a film financier. On page 43, Saeed Kamal is a student of Safdar Sultan, on page 68, an ASP, on page 82, a zonal manager of a company, on page 84, a Maulvi's son, on page 99, a film director, on page 143, a bodybuilder, on page 378, a young student who grew up to become a successful translator. Similarly, he is also the Ranjha of Lucky Star Theater and is also Mirza. Apart from them, on page 69, Anila Bilal is a lecturer and ASP's fiancée, on page 82, she is the lover of the zonal manager, on page 87, she is an actress in a stage drama named Anila Sassi, on page 99, she is a scriptwriter for a film. Apart from these important characters, Irshad Kabadiya, Irshad Driver, Jabbar the rioter, Jabbar the hotelier and Jabbar the collector, the mistress of the cameraman and Yasin the mechanic are all separate characters with similar names. The author has described their psychological situation in their lives in this way.

"Hum har mumkin israar karein ge, dekha jaye to misali haqeeqi sadme ka jo tasawwur is tehreer mein samne laya gaya hai yani aisa sadma jis ka dukh aap dunya mein kisi ek bhi shakhs ke saath baant na sakein, itna ghambheer aur dil hila dene wala almiya ke is par safhon ke safhe kale kiye ja sakte hain lekin hum aisa kuch bhi karne ka irada nahi rakhte kyunke hamein dusre bahut se afraad ka jaiza bhi lena hai jo shayad itne misali aur haqeeqi na hon lekin bahar haal husn ki surat e haal ka hissa hain. Misal ke taur par Swang Film Group ke memberan ke sadmaat jo apne apne taur par is umeed o beem mein mubtila hain ke aala paye ki film yeh film nahi ban sakti kabhi ban sakegi ya nahi. Aur Art aur Culture ke champion Hikmat Behzad ki zindagi bhar ke sadmaat mein khulne wale naye sadmaat ka baab. Apni gharelu tehzeeb ki khird afrozi ke champion Professor Safdar Sultan ka sadma ke Ala-ud-Din ke chiragh ka jinn bijli paida karne mein kotahi kyun karta hai. Professor ke shagird Saeed Kamal ka sadma ke Irshad kabariye ne Professor ke khird afrozi ke maswade ko kya waqai aage raddi ke bhau bech diya. Pyara nami bone ka kafi haqeeqi sadma ke jab woh Baby Katar ka wasl hasil karte mehroom reh jata hai. Aur is ke ilawa bhi dusre Saeed Kamal. Dusri Anila. Dusre sadme.(18)

Conclusion:

In Short lines it can be said that in "Hasan Ki Surat-e-Hal", wealth, fame, honor, status, legitimate and illegitimate fulfillment of sexual desires, struggle and conflict for dominance are the philosophy of life of this novel. Each character of this novel has its own metaphysics. This novel covers several sciences that are related to different aspects of life. And these are the qualities of this novel.

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